

Supplementary Information

Diffusive Gradients in Thin-Films technique for uranium monitoring along a salinity gradient: A comparative study on the performance of Chelex-100, Dow-PIWBA, Diphonix, and Lewatit FO 36 resin gels in the Scheldt Estuary

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Table S1 Sampling stations on the Scheldt estuary and Belgian coast.

Location	Geographical coordinates			Results available for each campaign ^a			
	Sampling station	Latitude	Longitude	2014	2019	2020	2021
Scheldt estuary	HEM	51°11.57'N	04°20.15'E	CH, P	CH, P, D	*	CH, P, D, L
	S22	51°14.20'N	04°23.70'E	CH, P	CH	CH, P, D, L	CH, P, D, L
	S15	51°18.80'N	04°16.40'E	CH, P	CH, P, D	CH, P, D, L	CH, P, D, L
	S12	51°21.90'N	04°13.50'E	CH, P	CH	CH, P, D, L	CH, P, D, L
	S09	51°22.20'N	04°04.20'E	CH, P	CH, P, D	CH, P, D, L	CH, P, D, L
	S07	51°26.10'N	03°59.30'E	CH, P	CH	CH, P, D, L	CH, P, D, L
	S04	51°20.50' N	03°50.50'E	CH, P	CH, P	*	*
	S01	51°24.80'N	03°34.40'E	CH, P	CH, P, D	*	CH, P, D, L
Zeebrugge harbour	HZ1	51°20.41'N	03°12.20'E			CH, P, D, L (l-t)	
	HZ2	51°19.87'N	03°11.97'E				P, D, L (l-t)

^a CH – Chelex-100; P – Dow-PIWBA; D – Diphonix; L – Lewatit FO 36; l-t – long term deployment.

* Missing data due to unfavorable weather conditions for DGT retrieval or loss of DGTs.

Table S2 Physico-chemical parameters of water from stations HEM–S01 during campaigns 2014–2021 (average values of n=2 obtained from upstream and downstream sampling).

Parameter	Year	Station							
		HEM	S22	S15	S12	S09	S07	S04	S01
Temperature (°C)	2014	7.40	7.40	7.40	7.00	6.40	6.10	6.00	6.00
	2019	8.90	8.75	8.90	8.90	8.25	8.10	8.05	7.95
	2020	8.80	8.25	8.30	8.25	7.80	8.05	8.05	7.61
	2021	8.30	8.40	8.00	8.10	7.10	6.50	5.90	6.30
pH	2014	7.80	7.90	7.90	8.00	8.00	8.09	8.10	8.05
	2019	7.81	7.88	7.90	8.00	8.04	8.01	8.04	8.01
	2020	8.38	8.16	8.09	7.97	8.04	8.06	8.05	8.04
	2021	7.73	7.78	7.94	7.96	7.90	7.95	7.98	7.96
Salinity	2014	0.9	1.6	3.7	5	8.4	11.4	16.7	25.2
	2019	0.3	1	2.3	4.9	9.6	14.8	19.5	25.7
	2020	0.2	0.4	3.1	3.9	9.9	14.9	20	25.3
	2021	0.4	0.7	4.7	6.8	11.3	14.5	18.8	24.9
Oxygen (mg L ⁻¹)	2014	8.8	8.0	8.0	8.0	7.7	10.7	11.6	12.3
	2019	9.5	9.6	9.8	11.5	11.1	11.7	12.2	11.5
	2020	8.7	9.3	10.8	11.0	11.2	11.5	11.4	11.8
	2021	7.2	7.6	9.8	10.5	11.1	11.6	11.9	12.3

Table S3 Physico-chemical parameters and concentrations of major cations, anions, and DOC analysed in the Scheldt Estuary (upstream sampling, 2014) and used as input data for the geochemical speciation of uranium.

Parameter	Station							
	HEM	S22	S15	S12	S09	S07	S04	S01
Salinity	1.0	2.0	4.0	5.4	9.7	12.8	16.8	24.0
Temperature (°C)	6.7	7.0	7.2	7.0	6.4	6.2	6.1	6.2
pH	7.8	7.9	7.9	8.0	8.0	8.1	8.1	8.1
Alkalinity (meq L ⁻¹)	3.9	3.9	3.8	3.7	3.6	3.5	3.3	2.9
O ₂ (mg L ⁻¹)	8.8	8.0	8.0	8.0	7.7	10.7	11.6	12.3
DOC (mg L ⁻¹)	6.925	6.923	4.712	7.988	5.244	1.851	1.683	1.135
Ca ²⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	93	101	118	129	170	193	231	290
K ⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	18	27	47	58	105	132	175	249
Mg ²⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	34	65	131	178	332	427	573	815
Na ⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	241	511	1,069	1,425	2,664	3,436	4,606	6,536
Cl ⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	510	1,075	2,414	2,979	5,847	7,563	10,621	16,536
SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	119	189	333	414	762	1,208	1,874	2,261
PO ₄ ³⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	0.24	0.24	0.26	0.23	0.25	0.23	0.20	0.15
NH ₄ ⁺ (mg L ⁻¹)	0.32	0.23	0.11	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.06
Si (mg L ⁻¹)	3.78	3.24	3.05	2.75	2.56	2.03	1.85	1.07
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	16.20	16.04	15.04	14.24	12.36	11.23	9.24	5.75
U (µg L ⁻¹)	1.07	1.2	1.32	1.54	1.92	2.18	2.73	2.82

Table S4 Matrix of Pearson-type correlation between salinity and dissolved uranium concentration at stations HEM–S01.

		Dissolved U concentration			
		2014	2019	2020	2021
Salinity	2014	0.957099			
	2019		0.985534		
	2020			0.987798	
	2021				0.982811